

Effect Service Quality and Customers Satisfactions on Customers Loyalty in The Fantasy Word

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Abstract:

The study aims to examine the effect of service quality and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty in Dunia Fantasi using quantitative, multiple linear regression. The result of this research there was influence between service quality to customer loyalty. There is influence between customer satisfaction to customer loyalty. Simultaneously quality of service and customer satisfaction to customer loyalty have positive and significant, resulted in the correlation value of 0.885 or (88.5%) with regression equation $Y = 2.418 + 0.565X_1 + 0.500X_2$ remaining another factor of 11.5% namely price, promotion, location, and others.

Keywords: Service Quality, Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, competition in business is a real thing. Customer loyalty is very important for the life of the company in Dunia Fantasi, after the interview survey in Dunia Fantasi, consumers feel less satisfied with the service provided by the officers, for the less friendly officer in serving the visitors and some of the officers less neat appearance so as to give the image less good, so that visitors do not want to visit again or do not make repeat purchases.

Service Quality:

Quality of service influence and stimulate consumers to buy the product again, because not in terms of product quality alone. In terms of service if the clerk to provide service excellent service can make customers happy heart.

With a friendly, kind, polite and courteous service is very influential on the feelings of customers who will buy again were the places - the place. Thus the sales volume can increase.

Customer Satisfaction:

Customer satisfaction in Dunia Fantasi is one of the factors that determine customer loyalty, based on the result of an interview survey with the visitors in the field, the visitors feel disappointed because there are some less good rides such as star war rides for many play tools that are not functioning properly thus visitors feel not fasting for the services provided in terms of quality of service and in terms of price quality.

Realizing this, Ancol realized that the need for added value to be able to continue to excel in business competition, one of which is in terms of innovation.

PROBLEM FORMULATION

The formulation of the problems that exist in this research is as follows:

1. Does the quality of service affect customer loyalty in Fantasy World?
2. Does customer satisfaction affect customer loyalty in Fantasy World?
3. Does the quality of service and customer satisfaction affect the customer loyalty in World Fantasy?

LITERATURE

Quality of service

Quality of Service is an attitude or way of serving customers so that customers get the satisfaction that includes speed, accuracy, friendliness, and comfort. According to Fands Tjiptono (2005, p.58-59). With services among others,

- 1) Physical evidence (Tangible)
- 2) Trust (Realibility)
- 3) Reliability (Reability)
- 4) Responsiveness
- 5) Assurance (Assurance)
- 6) Emphaty.

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction can be defined as a condition in which the needs, wants, and expectations of consumers can be met through the products consumed. According to Walker, et al. (2001: 35). Dimensions that researchers will do is among others :

- 1) Better Characteristics (better)
- 2) Faster Characteristics (Faster)
- 3) Characteristics of cheaper (cheap)
- 4) Newer Characteristics (newer)

Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty is a behavioral impulse to make repeated purchases and to build customer loyalty to a product or service generated by the business entity that takes a long time through a process of purchasing that occurs repeatedly. Olson (Trisno Mushanto, 2004:128). To measure consumer loyalty researchers will shave dimensions used include:

- (1) Make repeated purchases on a regular basis, Need recognition,
- (2) Buying outside the product / service line.
- (3) Recommend other products,
- (4) Showing immunity from the attraction of similar products from competitors.

FRAMEWORK

Figure 1. The framework of the Research

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The hypothesis is a temporary answer to a suspicious problem from a field study. Based on the principal problems studied then in this study the authors propose the following hypothesis:

1. There is influence quality of service to customer loyalty in Fantasy World.
2. There is influence customer satisfaction on customer loyalty in Fantasy World.
3. There is the influence of quality of service and customer satisfaction simultaneously to customer loyalty in Fantasy World.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research was a survey method with descriptive and associative explanatory techniques. Descriptive and explanatory techniques are used to obtain information about determinants of service quality and customer satisfaction and their influence on customer loyalty. The population in this research amounted to 3000 Visitors in the fantasy world. The number of samples taken is 97 sespondents; a sampling of populations is randomly based on the probability frequencies of all members of the population. To get the perception of the respondent's data related to the research variables, each variable is composed of dimensions, which are then operationalized against the indicators. The operational variables of the research are as follows:

Research Variables

1. Independent variable (Independent variable)

As proposed by Sugiyono (2009), the free variable is a variable that affects or becomes the cause of the change or the emergence of the dependent variable. In this study, quality of service, in this case, is the first independent (X1), and customer satisfaction is the second independent variable (X2).

2. Dependent Variable

This variable is often called the dependent variable, that is the variable that is influenced or the result, because of the free variable (Sugiyono 2009). In this study, customer loyalty is a dependent variable (Y).

Operational Definition

1. Quality of service

Service quality can be measured using five dimensions. The five dimensions according to Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry (1985) in Tjiptono (2005) with the physical dimension (tangible), trust (reliability), responsive, assurance, empathy.

2. Customer Satisfaction

Kotler and Keller (2009: 138) interpret satisfaction as the feeling of pleasure or disappointment of a person arising from comparing the perceived performance of a product (or outcome) to their expectations. Customers will feel satisfied if the results of their evaluation indicate that the service they feel good. In this case, researchers will take dimensions, among others product quality, service quality, emotional, customer, price, and cost.

3. Customer loyalty

Olson (in Trisno Mushanto, 2004 128) argues that customer loyalty is a behavioral impulse to repeat purchase and to build customer loyalty to a product or service produced by that enterprise that takes a long time through a buying process that occurs repeatedly. To measure customer loyalty researchers will shave dimensions used among others re-buy regularly, buying between product lines and services, refer to others, showing immunity to competitiveness

Hypothesis Analysis and Testing Technique

1) Testing the Assumption of Regression Model

a. Normality test

Normality test to test free variable data (X) and the dependent variable (Y) on the regression equation produced, whether abnormal distributed. Normality test data can be done by looking at Normal P-P Plot. If the plot has a straight line pattern, the data is normally distributed, and vice versa if the plot does not show a straight line, the data is not normally distributed.

b. Heteroskedity Test

Heteroskeditas test to determine the equal or not variance of one observation with another observation. Assessment analysis of heteroskedity assumption of Spss output result through scatterplot graph between Z prediction (ZPRED) which is the result of the independent variable (predicted X-Y source), and its residual value (SRESID) is dependent variable (Y = Y axis Y real prediction).

c. Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity is the condition of the existence of a linear relationship or a high correlation between each independent variable in the regression model. The multi-collinearity test with SPSS is done by looking at the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) benchmark value. The criterion used is, if the value of VIF is around number 1, it is said to have no multicollinearity problem.

d. Autocorrelation.

Autocorrelation test was conducted to test whether there was a correlation between observation with previous observation data. Autocorrelation can be measured by Durbin-Watson value, where if its Durbin-Watson value is close to 2, it can be concluded that there is no autocorrelation problem.

2) Validity Testing and Instrument Reliability

a. Validity

Validity testing is done by calculating the correlation between each statement with the total score. The formula of the Pearson correlation is as follows:

$$r = \frac{n(\sum XY) - (\sum X \sum Y)}{\sqrt{\{n \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

Sumber: Umi Narimawati (2010:42)

So get the basic take the following decisions:

- a. If r result is positive, and r result > r table, then the data is valid.
- b. If r result is not positive, and r result is < r table, then the data is invalid.

b. Reliability

Reliability with regard to the degree of consistency and stability of data or findings. In a positivistic (quantitative) view, a data is declared reliable if two or more data researchers in the same object produce the same data, or a group of data, when split into two, indicates data that is not different (Sugiyono, 2009: 456). Alpha Cronbach formula (Priyatno, 2008: 25)

$$\alpha_{\text{standardized}} = \frac{K \bar{r}}{(1 + (K - 1) \bar{r})}$$

The measuring tool is said to be reliable, if:

- a. Cronbach's Alpha produced > 0.60 then the research instrument's grain is declared reliable.
- b. Cronbach's Alpha produced < 0.60 then the research instrument's grain is declared not reliable.

3) Data Analysis Method

a. Frequency

Analysis of data used to determine the assessment of respondents required assessment tabulation table frequency.

b. Hypothesis testing

The associative hypothesis is a presumption of the presence or absence of a signification relationship between two or more variables (Sugiyono, 2009: 211).

1) Two-way test (Two Tall Test)

Used when the null hypothesis (H0) is hunted "equals," and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) reads "not equal to" (H0 =, Ha ≠).

The null hypothesis (H0): there is no influence between X and Y

Alternative hypothesis (Ha): there is an influence between X and Y

H0: p = 0 (meaning no effect)

Ha: p ≠ 0 (meaning there is an influence)

p = the correlation value in the hypothesized formulation.

If the p value (sig) < (0.05), then the independent variable individually affects the dependent variable, which means H0 successfully rejected.

2) Regression Analysis

a. Partial Test (t test)

T test is done to know or test the significance of the influence of a variable X (service quality or customer satisfaction) partially to Y (customer loyalty).

b. Anova Test (F Test)

Anova test or F test is performed to know or test the significance of the effect of the X variable (service quality or customer satisfaction) together to Y (customer loyalty).

Basic decision making:

1) If F arithmetic < F table then H0 is accepted

2) If F arithmetic > F table then H0 rejected Or if the value of significance < alpha (0.005) then H0 is rejected.

c. the coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination is intended to find out how much contribution or percentage of the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable.

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION RESULT

Statistical Test Results

1) Normality Test

Table 1. One Sample Kolmogorov Smirnov

		Unstandardized Residual
N		97
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0E-7
	Std. Deviation	3.84342325
	Absolute	.089
Most Extreme Differences	Positive	.089
	Negative	-.041
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.875
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.428

a. Test distribution is Normal.

2) Hypothesis Testing

a. Quality of Service (X1) on Customer Loyalty (Y)

Table 2. Correlation Coefficient Test Results Quality Service Against Customer Loyalty

Correlations			
		loyalitas pelanggan	kepuasan pelanggan
Pearson Correlation	loyalitas pelanggan	1.000	.745
	kepuasan pelanggan	.745	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	loyalitas pelanggan	.	.000
	kepuasan pelanggan	.000	.
N	loyalitas pelanggan	97	97
	kepuasan pelanggan	97	97

Results of data processing between the quality of service with customer loyalty resulted in a correlation value of 0.745 (74.5%); thus there is a strong positive relationship. From the data above shows that the value of the determinant coefficient of 74.5% indicates that variations in the increase or decrease in customer loyalty variables can be explained by the service quality variable of 74.5% other factors beyond these two variables are 25.50%.

Table 3. Regression Test Results in Quality of Service Against Customer Loyalty

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	3.754	3.135		
1 kualitas pelayanan	.917	.084	.745	10.886	.000

a. Dependent Variable: loyalitas pelanggan
Sumber : Hasil pengolahan data

Regression value is seen $Y = 3.754 + 0.917 X$ (Service Quality) so that the pure value of loyalty variable of the customer without influenced by service quality variable equal to 3,754. The result of a hypothesis test is t_{value} 10,886 where the t_{table} is 1.661 so that ($t_{value} 10.886 > t_{table} 1.661$) so that (H_0) is rejected and (H_a) accepted means there is influence between service quality to customer loyalty.

b. Customer Satisfaction (X2) Against Customer Loyalty (Y)

Table 4. Results of Correlation Coefficient of Customer Satisfaction Against Customer Loyalty

Correlations			
		loyalitas pelanggan	kepuasan pelanggan
loyalitas pelanggan	Pearson Correlation	1	.745**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	97	97
kepuasan pelanggan	Pearson Correlation	.745**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	97	97

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results of data processing between Customer Satisfaction with customer loyalty resulted in a correlation value of 0.745 (74.5%); thus there is a strong positive relationship. From the above data shows that the value of the determinant coefficient of 61.5% indicates that variations in the increase or decrease in variable Customer loyalty can be explained by service quality variable of 61.5% other factors beyond the two variables by 38.49%.

Table 5. Regression Test Results of Customer Satisfaction Against Customer Loyalty

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	6.358	2.903		
1 kepuasan pelanggan	.813	.075	.745	10.872	.000

a. Dependent Variable: loyalitas pelanggan

Regression value seen $Y = 6,358 + 0.813 X$ (customer satisfaction) so that pure value of customer loyalty variable without influenced by customer satisfaction variable equal to 6,358. Hypothesis test results seen t_{value} 10.872 where t_{table} 1.661 so that (t_{value} 10.872 > t_{tabel} 1.661) so that (H0) rejected and (Ha) accepted means there is influence between customer satisfaction with customer loyalty.

c. Quality of Service and Customer Satisfaction Simultaneously to customer loyalty

Table 6. The Correlation Coefficient Test Results of Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty

Correlations				
		loyalitas pelanggan	kepuasan pelanggan	kualitas pelayanan
loyalitas pelanggan	Pearson Correlation	1	.745**	.745**
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	97	97	97
kepuasan pelanggan	Pearson Correlation	.745**	1	.625**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	97	97	97
kualitas pelayanan	Pearson Correlation	.745**	.625**	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	97	97	97

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

From the above table can be concluded correlation of 0.745 or (74.5%); thus there is a very strong positive relationship between independent variables (service quality and customer satisfaction) simultaneously to customer loyalty. Thus the results of a determinant coefficient test of 0.745 (74.5%) thus the variance increase or decrease in variable Customer loyalty can be explained by independent variables (service quality and customer satisfaction) with other factors of 0.255 or (25.5%).

Table 7. Determinant Coefficient Test Results (R-Square) Service Quality and customer satisfaction with customer loyalty

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	2.418	2.845		
1 kualitas pelayanan	.565	.092	.459	6.161	.000
kepuasan pelanggan	.500	.081	.458	6.146	.000

a. Dependent Variable: loyalitas pelanggan

Sumber : Hasil pengolahan data

Table 8. Correlation Coefficient Test Result (t test) Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty Simultaneously

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	2679.820	1	2679.820	118.501	.000 ^b
Residual	2148.365	95	22.614		
Total	4828.186	96			

a. Dependent Variable: loyalitas pelanggan
 b. Predictors: (Constant), kualitas pelayanan

$$Y = 2.418 + 0.565X_1 + 0.500X_2$$

Based on the results of data processing:

- The constant value of 2,418 indicates the pure value of customer loyalty variable without being influenced by the independent variable of service quality and customer satisfaction.
- Regression value (β_1) quality of service amounted to 0.565 indicates there is a variable contribution quality of service means that if the quality of service quality increases 1 point, then it will give influence to the strengthening of customer loyalty variable equal to regression value. Hypothesis test value $t_value\ 6.161 > t_table\ 1.661$ so H_0 rejected and H_a accepted means there is influence between the quality of service to customer loyalty. The probability value of the result of 0.000 where the value of $\alpha = 0.05$ thus ($\rho = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$) because the probability far below the alpha value then the quality of service variables have a positive and significant relationship to customer loyalty.
- Regression value (β_2) Customer satisfaction of 0.567 indicates there is a variable contribution customer satisfaction means that if the quality of service quality increases 1 point, then it will give influence to the strengthening of variable Customer loyalty equal to regression value. Hypothesis test value $t_value\ 6.146 > t_table\ 1.661$ so H_0 rejected and H_a accepted means there is influence between the quality of service to customer loyalty. The probability value of the result of 0.000 where the value of $\alpha = 0.05$ thus ($\rho = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$) because the probability far below the alpha value then the quality of service variables have a positive and significant relationship to customer loyalty.

The results of simultaneous hypothesis test can be seen as follows:

Table 9. Anova Test Results

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	2679.820	1	2679.820	118.501	.000 ^b
Residual	2148.365	95	22.614		
Total	4828.186	96			

a. Dependent Variable: loyalitas pelanggan
 b. Predictors: (Constant), kualitas pelayanan

The result of data processing on hypothesis test simultaneously yielded Fcount equal to 118,501 where F_table at $df(2:93)$ show F_table equal to 1,858 thus ($F_value\ 118,501 > F_table\ 1,858$) then (H_a) accepted, value ($\rho = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$) because probability far below the alpha value than the independent variable (service quality and customer satisfaction) simultaneously have a positive and significant relationship to customer loyalty.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

- There is influence between service quality to customer loyalty where result of hypothesis test seen that $t_value\ 6,161$ and $t_table\ 1.661$ so $t_value\ 6,161 > t_table\ 1.661$ so that (H_0) rejected and (H_a) accepted, correlation value equal to 0.565 (83,3%) with regression equation value $Y = 2.418 + 0.836 X$ (quality of service) thus the pure value of customer loyalty variable without being influenced by the quality of service variables of 6.839 while the

regression value of 0.565 X is the contribution of the variable quality of service. The probability value of the result of 0.000 where $\alpha = 0.05$ thus ($\rho = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$) because the probability far below the alpha value then the quality of service variables have a positive and significant influence on customer loyalty.

2. There is influence between Customer Satisfaction with Customer Loyalty where the result of hypothesis test shows that t_value 6.146 and t_table 1.661 so t_value 6.146 > t_table 1.661 so that (H₀) is rejected and (H_a) accepted, the correlation value is 0.565 (56,5%) factor another value of 44.5% ie, price, promotion, location and others. with the value of regression equation $Y = 6.358 + 0.813 X$ (Customer satisfaction) thus the pure value of customer loyalty variable without influenced by customer satisfaction variable of 6.358 while the regression value of 0.813 X is contribution variable Customer Satisfaction. Result probability value 0.000 where $\alpha = 0.05$ thus ($\rho = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$) because the probability far below the alpha value then Customer Satisfaction variables have a positive and significant influence on customer loyalty.
3. Simultaneously the quality of service and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty has a positive and significant relationship. Resulted the correlation value of 0.885 or (88.5%) with regression equation $Y = 2.418 + 0.565X_1 + 0.500X_2$ remaining other factor of 11.5% ie price, promotion, location and others. Thereby the pure value of customer loyalty is 2,450 without any contribution of independent variable, while the contribution of variable of service quality is 0.561, while the contribution of customer satisfaction variable is 0.567, from hypothesis test result is seen (F_value 168,497 > F_table 1.858) (H₀) is rejected, the value ($\rho = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$). Thus the results of a determinant coefficient test of 0.784 (78.4%) variance increase or decrease in variable customer loyalty can be explained by independent variables (service quality and customer satisfaction) so that other factors of 0.216 or (21.6%).

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of data processing and conclusions on research, the suggestions in the study are as follows:

1. To further increase customer loyalty World Fantasy needs to consider the elements of variable quality of service and customer satisfaction.
2. To further increase Loyalty needs to consider customers variable elements of customer satisfaction — price one of them where the ability to influence the market, non-price attribute. The World Fantasy company should further enhance its advertising to be known much closer to consumers.
3. In terms of customer perception to the quality of service and customer satisfaction

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